

International

MAY 6
2024

scientific and
practical conference

2024

STDF
Science technology &
Digital finance

**The main directions of socio-economic
development of New Uzbekistan:
problems and solutions**

MINISTRY OF HIGHER EDUCATION, SCIENCE AND INNOVATION
OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN
JIZZAKH BRANCH OF THE NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF UZBEKISTAN
NAMED AFTER MIRZO ULUGBEK

Scientific journal of Science technology & Digital finance

The main directions of socio-economic development of New Uzbekistan:
problems and solutions collection of materials of the international scientific
and practical conference on the topic

(May 6, 2024)

Jizzakh-2024

In the collection of materials of the conference, the role and role of Science, Education and production in the era of globalization, the pressing problems of the issues of interaction of these processes, feedback on their solutions were presented by mature specialists of the field.

In addition, research on the scientific and practical topic, carried out in the economics, Exact Sciences, Natural Sciences and socio-humanities during the globalization period, information is presented in the scientific and practical fields, which includes the latest innovative technologies in the fields of production.

It can be argued that this collection is one of the specific intersections of current thoughts and innovative ideas of the world of science. This scientific and practical conference was actively attended by professors and scientific researchers engaged in scientific research in Uzbekistan and foreign countries. In increasing the position of the scientific and practical conference, the professors and teachers of domestic and foreign higher educational institutions made a significant contribution.

Professors and teachers of foreign higher educational institutions who actively participated in the work of the conference made a worthy contribution to the high level of interaction with scientists of our country. The processes of international cooperation with foreign countries and exchange with them in the field of Science in the era of globalization have a positive effect on the development of Higher Education, the fields of Science and production. The materials of this conference are special in that they include a wide range of research, from theoretical developments to practical solutions, demonstrating the diversity of approaches and directions in this area.

In conclusion, it should be noted that this scientific and practical conference will be a very useful collection for everyone who is interested in modern research in the fields of further development of Higher Education, Science, Education and production in the era of globalization. The authors are responsible for the content and quality of the articles and abstracts included in the collection.

ORGANIZATIONS ACTIVELY PARTICIPATING IN THE CONFERENCE

1. Ministry of Higher Education, Science and Innovation of the Republic of Uzbekistan
2. Jizzakh branch of the National university of Uzbekistan named after Mirzo Ulugbek
3. Kazan Federal University (Russia)
4. Fast support and result LLC
5. Micro-Telecom LLC

ORGANIZING COMMITTEE MEMBERS:

1. Baboev A.M.	– Deputy director for Youth Affairs and spiritual and educational affairs of the Jizzakh branch of the National University of Uzbekistan named after Mirzo Ulugbek, chairman;
2. Uralov A.I.	– Deputy Director for Scientific Affairs and Innovation, Vice chairman
3. Soy M.P.	– Head of the Department “Economy and tourism”, Associate Professor, member;
4. Mukhtarov B.A.	– Associate professor of the Department “Economy and tourism”, member;
5. Kuchimov A.H.	– Associate professor of the Department “Economy and tourism”, member;
6. Zulfakarova L.F.	– Kazan Federal University, Associate Professor, member;
7. Alimov N.N.	– Dean of the Faculty of “Psychology”, candidate of Pedagogical Sciences, Associate Professor, member;
8. Alibaev S.X.	– Dean of the Faculty of “Applied mathematics”, (PhD), member;
9. Karshiyev A.A.	– Head of the Department “Information systems and technologies”, (PhD), member;
10. Halimov U.	– Head of Graduate Department, (PhD), member;
11. Nasirov B.U	– Head of the Department “Social Sciences and Physical Culture”, (PhD), member;
12. Mustafokulov M.	– Head of Department “Biotechnology”, (PhD), member;
13. Sindorov L.	– Head of the Department “Uzbek language and literature”, (PhD), member;
14. Alibekov D.A	Head of the Department “Family Psychology”, (PhD), member;
15. Sharipov X.F.	– Head of the department “Applied mathematics”, member;
16. Kayumov O.A.	– Head of the department “Computer science and programming”, (PhD), member;
17. Norbekova B.Sh.	– Head of the department “Youth psychology”, (PhD), member;
18. Jurayev M.M.	– Head of the Department “Foreign languages”, member;
19. Kamolov D.R	– Teacher of the Department "Social Sciences and Physical Culture", Secretary.

Editor in chief:	Soy M.P.- Head of the Department "Economy and tourism", Associate Professor
Editorial board	Bobanazarova J.Kh.- Professor of the Department of Economics and tourism
	Zulfakarova L.F.- Kazan Federal University, Associate Professor
	Garifullin R.R.- Kazan Federal University, Associate Professor
	Mukhtarov B.A.- Associate professor of the Department "Economy and tourism"
	Kuchimov A.H.- Associate professor of the Department "Economy and tourism"
	Samadkulov M.I.- Associate professor of the Department "Economy and tourism"
	Saidakhmedova D.S.- Associate professor of the Department "Economy and tourism"
	Sharipov X.F.- Head of the department "Applied mathematics", Associate Professor
	Nasirov B.U- Head of the Department "Social Sciences and Physical Culture", Associate Professor
Technical editors:	Nizametdinov A.A.- Senior lecturer of the Department "Economics and tourism"
	Saitov S.A.- Senior lecturer of the Department "Economics and tourism"
	Najmiddinov D.R.- Assistant of the Department "economy and tourism"
Secretary of organizing committee:	Kamolov D.R- Teacher of the Department "Social Sciences and Physical Culture"

INTRODUCTION

In our country, large-scale work is carried out on the modernization of the higher education system, the introduction of modern forms and technologies of education, the improvement of the directions of training specialists. In the strategy of action on the five priority areas of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan, important issues of radical updating the content of Personnel Training, creating the necessary conditions for the training of highly qualified specialists on the basis of international templates are outlined. At the moment, special attention is paid to the development of the material and technical base of the Institute.

Science and innovative research in it are at the center of these changes and serve as catalysts for progress in various fields such as the exact and natural sciences, economics, Information Technology, social and humanities, and so on. The main goal in the idea of the new Uzbekistan is to open new opportunities for solving and developing technologies and current social problems by investing in research and innovation.

The problems waiting for their solution to improve the effect of reforms in this direction carried out in our republic, create conditions for the comprehensive and rapid development of the state and society, modernize our country and liberalize all spheres of life will find their solution in the process of discussions, discussions and scientific lectures between high-potential scientific schools. The conference will discuss the results of advanced fundamental and Applied Research, increasing the intellectual prestige of our country and commercializing the results of research.

The main purpose of the conference is to develop scientifically based proposals for the socio-economic development of the Republic of Uzbekistan, solve the tasks facing production enterprises, educational institutions and also other industry organizations by proposing new innovative solutions, studying potential solutions. In addition, the conference aims to synchronize the results of scientific research carried out in educational institutions and research institutes. Through the Scientific Reports at our conference, we are looking forward to opening a new path for young researchers, doctoral students and very talented students to communicate with the scientific community.

As a result of the conference, the environment of mutual scientific and creative cooperation between professors, students, scientific worker-researcher, independent researcher, scientists and specialists of related fields and the exchange of feedback and experience will be created, which will be combined on the path of development of Science and technology. The conference also provides for the active promotion of the intellectual prestige of our country and the commercialization of the results of research. In short, we believe that the rapid implementation of such processes as having practical skills in the training of mature qualified specialists, gaining experience, developing the modern educational process and establishing systematic work on linking new teaching processes to industry professionals will be an impetus for us to achieve great heights.

It should be noted that special attention is paid to the reform of the educational system, the conditions being created for young people, the emergence of their abilities and talents, the formation of loyalty. After all, loyalty to the Fatherland, el-yurt, is a great virtue.

TARIXIY OBIDALARNING INSON MA'NAVIYATIGA TA'SIRI

International
scientific and
practical conference

Google Scholar

Tolibboyev Dilshod Muhammadiyevich

O'zbekiston Milliy universitetining Jizzax filiali "Ijtimoiy fanlar va jismoniy madaniyat" kafedrasida katta o'qituvchisi

Sufxiddinov Sayfiddin Qahramon og'li, Miyzamov Zubaydulla Eshmamat o'g'li

O'zbekiston Milliy universiteti Jizzax filiali 3-bosqich talabalari

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolamizda yurtimizdagi hamda dunyodagi tarixiy obidalarning xalqimizga uning o'tmishi va ulug'vor tarixini eslatib turuvchi manbaa ekanligini keltirib o'tamiz.

Kalit so'zlar: Tarixiy obidalar, xalqimiz o'tmishi, ulug'vor tarix, qadimgi Misr, "Kuch-adolatdadir", Samarqand, "Sayqali ro'yi zamin", Sherdor, Tillakori, Ulug'bek, Bibixonim;

Аннотация: В данной статье мы отмечаем, что исторические памятники нашей страны и мира являются источником напоминания нашему народу о его прошлом и славной истории.

Ключевые слова: Исторические памятники, прошлое нашего народа, славная история, Древний Египет, «Сила справедлива», Самарканд, «Сайкали ройи замин», Шердор, Тиллакори, Улугбек, Бибиханим;

Abstract: In this article, we mention that the historical monuments of our country and the world are a source of reminding our nation of its past and glorious history.

Key words: Historical monuments, the past of our people, glorious history, ancient Egypt, "Strength is just", Samarkand, "Saikali royi zamin", Sherdor, Tillakori, Ulug'bek, Bibikhanim;

KIRISH

Har bir davlatda xalqining o'tmishi va ulug'vor tarixini eslatib turuvchi tarixiy obidalar va yodgorliklar mavjud. Ushbu yodgorliklar orqali inson ma'naviy ozuqa oladi, o'z davlatining tarixidan faxrlanadi va g'urur tuyg'usini his etadi. Dunyoda inson qo'li bilan yaratilgan va necha ming yillardan beri saqlanib, o'z jozibasini yo'qotmay kelayotgan tarixiy obidalar ko'plab uchraydi. Ammo har birining alohida o'rni, nufuzi va ahamiyati bor. Tarixdan bizga ma'lumki inson zoti san'atni qadrlagan va go'zallikka intilib kelgan. Mana shu hislatlari orqali mohir qo'llari bilan aqlga sig'dirib bo'lmas darajadagi yangiliklarni yaratdi. Ular qatoridan fan yutuqlari, san'at sohasidagi ishlar va albatta me'morchilik joy oladi.

Inson bugungi kun bilangina yashab moziyga nazar solmas ekan o'tmishi va an'alarini unutib qo'yadi. O'z tarixini bilmagan xalqning esa kelajagi yo'qdir.

Qadimgi Misr tarixiga nazar tashlasak, ular o'z rivojlanishi davomida asriy an'ana va qadriyatlariga sodiq qolib, chetdan kirgan yangiliklarni o'z an'alariga moslab keraklilarinigina qabul qilganlar. Qurilish, fan, tabobat sohalarida ham qadriyatlariga sodiq qolganlar.

ADABIYOTLAR TAHLILI VA METODOLOGIYA.

Vatanimiz hududida ham o'tmishdan sado beruvchi ko'plab tarixiy me'moriy obidalar bizgacha yetib kelgan. Ular mahobati, o'ziga xos me'moriy uslubi va did bilan ishlangan naqshlari orqali nafaqat ichki sayyohlarni, balki xorijiy san'atsevarlarni ham jalb etmoqda. Ushbu obidalarni ziyorat qilish yosh avlod qalbida ham g'urur, ham iftixor tuyg'usini uyg'otadi.

Vatanining o'tmishidan faxrlangan inson esa o'z oldiga ajdodlarga munosib avlod bo'lishni maqsad qilib oladi. Qadimda yaratilgan har bir tarixiy obida bizni kechagi kun bilan chambarchas holda bog'lab turadi va ana shu davr nafasini his etishimizga ko'maklashadi. Inson ma'naviyatiga ta'sir qiluvchi kuchlar qatorida tarixiy obidalar o'rni alohida ta'kidlanayotgani bejiz emas. Bunday binolar inson qo'l mehnati, nozik didi va betakror g'oyalari mahsulidir. Inson omili esa bugungi kungacha jahon hamjamiyati tomonidan yuqori baholab kelinadi. Tarixda bunday loyihalarni qudratli davlatlarga mablag' bilan taminlay olgan xolos.

Sohibqiron Amir Temur aytganlaridek: “Kuch-qudratimizga shubha qilsang, biz qurgan binolarga boq”. Bu jumlaning o'zi ham ulug' davlatchilik tariximizni bizga eslatib turadi. Tarixiy obidalarga tashrif buyurgan inson xuddi o'tmishga, sehrli diyorga tushib qolgandek his qiladi o'zini va ana shu davr hayot tarzi ko'z oldida gavdalanadi. Tarixiy obidalar barpo etilishida ishlatilgan zarra qumdan tortib, mislsiz darajada betakror naqshlar va zarhal bezaklargacha bo'lgan barcha unsurlar go'yo tilga kirib ana shu davr haqida tashrif buyuruvchiga so'zlab bergandek tuyuladi. Mustaqillikning dastlabki yillaridanoq tarixiy obidalarga bo'lgan e'tiborning yuqori darajada bo'lishi ham ularning kelajak avlod uchun nechog'lik ahamiyatli ekanligidan nishonadir. Yoshlarni ushbu obidalarning har bir qismini mukammal o'rganishi va qalban his etishiga imkon yaratish borasida Prezidentimiz Shavkat Mirziyoyevning talabalarning o'qish yili davomida amaliyot soatlarini oshirishga doir qarorlari ijtimoiy-gumanitar fanlar bo'yicha tahsil olayotgan yoshlar uchun katta imkoniyatlar darvozasini ochib berdi. Bunday obidalarni ko'rish orqali har kim ma'naviy ozuqa oladi, shu bilan birga ruhan tetiklashadi.

Birgina Samarqand misolida olib qarajak, u yerni “Sayqali ro'yi zamin” deb atalishi bejiz emas. Bu hududda Sherdor, Tillakori, Ulug'bek, Bibixonim madrasalari va ko'plab boshqa tarixiy binolar joylashgan. Ularning har biri takrorlanmas go'zallikka ega. Shu xususiyatlar orqali Registon maydoni butun dunyo xalqlarini o'ziga jalb etib kelmoqda. Ushbu maydonda joylashgan Tillakori madrasasi tarixiga nazar tashlasak, madrasa 1646-1660-yillar davomida qurib bitkazilgan bo'lib, qurilish ishlariga Samarqand hokimi Bahodir Yalangto'sh homiylik qilgan. Madrasa karvonsaroy asosi ustiga qurilgan.

Dastlab “Yalangto'shbiy kichik madrasasi” deb nomlangan. Madrasa qurilishida yana boshqa bir maskan qurishga yetadigan miqdordagi mablag' ishlatilgani uchun “Tillakori” deb yuritila boshlangan. Madrasa aql bovar qilmas darajada serhashamligi bilan boshqalaridan ajrab turadi. Har bir peshtoq chuqur ravoqli qilib ishlangan va o'z navbatida bu katta mehnat va mahorat talab etgan.

Qurilishda eng mohir pardoachilar, me'morlar ishtirok etgan. Yana bir ajib tomoni xonaqoh to'riga marmardan jimjimadar mehrob va zinapoyali minbar ishlangan. Bino

ravoqida marmarga pardozi ishlari 1659-1660-yillar tugatilgani o'yib yozilgan. Birgina pardozi ishi bunday uzoq vaqt talab qilganligi ham madrasa yuqori did bilan bezatilganining isbotidir.

Tashrif buyuruvchini birinchi navbatda zarhal va ko'zni qamashtiruvchi bezakli naqshlar o'ziga rom etadi. Koshinlarning rangi esa takrorlanmas darajada go'zaldir, tadqiqotlar davomida ham bunga o'xshash rang yarata olinmadi. Baland gumbazlaridagi koshinlari feruza rangda bo'lib, o'ziga xos ulug'vorlik kasb etgan. Har bir bezak takrorlanmasligi va uyg'unligi bilan inson ko'zini qamashtiradi. Bezak mavzularining boyligi, naqshlarning haddan tashqari xilma-xilligi va bo'rtma yozuvlarning jozibasi boshqa hech bir binoda takrorlanmaydi. Mehrobdagi o'yma kosachalar zarhallanib Qur'oni Karim oyatlaridan olingan yozuvlar orqali bo'rtma shaklda to'ldirilgan. Madrasaning eshiklaridan tortib ravoqlarigacha alohida did va e'tibor bilan bezatilgan. Har bir eshik murakkab naqsh va xattotlik uslubidagi yozuvlar bilan pardozlangan. Hali obida ichiga kirmasdan inson ko'zi zarhal bezaklardan qamasha boshlaydi. Hovli sahni 50x50 metr bo'lib, hammayoq noyob marmarlar bilan qoplangan. Hujralar tobadoniga panjaralar ishlangan. Har bir hujra yoz kunlari salqin, qishda esa iliq bo'lgan. Madrasani ko'rgan insonning me'mor mahoratiga tan bermasdan iloji yo'q.

Yurtimizdagi ertaknamo shahar hisoblanmish Ko'hna Xivada ham ko'plab o'tmish ulug'vorligidan sado beruvchi obidalar mavjud. Ulardan biri Kalta Minoridir. Minora yurtimizdagi barcha binolardan sir-sinoati, jozibasi, asl holda saqlanganligi va hashamdorligi bilan ajralib turadi. Minora 1853-yildan bunyod etila boshlagan va oxiriga yetkazilmagan. Shunday bo'lsa ham hanuz tarixnavislarni jalb etmoqda. Tashrif buyuruvchini lol qoldiruvchi jihatlardan biri poydevorning 15 metr chuqurlikda joylashganligidir. Minora balandligi 29 metr. Agarda oxirigacha qurilganda 100 metrni tashkil etgan bo'lardi. Minoraga quyosh nurlari to'liq tushadi. Shunga qaramasdan birorta bezakning tovlanish xususiyati yo'qolmagan. Quyosh tik chiqqan payt naqshlar nuri ko'zni qamashtiradi. Bino mustahkam bo'lishi uchun pastdan yuqoriga qarab torayib borgan. Har bir qarich joy takrorlanmas, nafis geometrik naqshlar bilan

bezatilgan. Nomlanishi esa uning konussimon ko'rinishiga qarab belgilangan. Inson ko'ziga juda ham bahaybat va salobatli bo'lib ko'rinadi. Minoraga yog'och zinalar orqali 2-qavatdan kiriladi. Bezash jarayonida ishlatilgan ranglar tarkibi hanuz sirligicha qolmoqda. Zukko pardozechilarning hech bir ishi qayta takrorlanmagan. Hududda shunday muhit yaratilganki, u yerga kimgach, barcha narsani unutib o'tmish zarvaraqlari uzra hayol sura boshlaysiz.

Insonni lol qoldiruvchi jihatlardan yana biri, ayrim binolarda butun boshli bir xona devor ichiga o'yib ishlangan tokchlarga qo'yilgan sham orqali isitilgan. Hatto Xorazmdagi Juma masjidda imomning so'zlari devor teshiklari orqali butun hududga tiniq holda yetib borgan. Hududlarda yerdan zax ko'tarilmasligi uchun inshoot hovlisiga tut daraxti ekilgan. Bularning bari o'sha davr me'morlarining zakovati, uzoqni ko'ra olishi va o'z kasbining fidoiysi ekanligini isbotlaydi. Turli vositalarning sinoati hanuz topilmagani esa har bir bino qurilishidagi ishlar qayta takrorlanmaganligi va kasb siridan dalolat.

Har bir hududda o'zgacha me'morchilik uslubi bor. Vodiy ham bundan mustasno emas. Har bir tarixiy obida singari Qo'qon shahrining ramzi hisoblangan Xudoyorxon o'rdasi ham maxsus jihatlari bilan boshqalaridan keskin farq qiladi. Inshoot XIX asr 2-yarmida Xudoyorxon farmoniga asosan me'mor Mir Ubaydulla rahbarligida bunyod etilgan. Koshinlarni rishtonlik mohir usta Abdulla mahorat bilan ishlagan. Bino tepalikda baland g'ishtin poydevor bilan qurilgan. O'ziga xos tomonlaridan biri u yerda 100 ga yqain katta-kichik xonalari borligidadir.

Markazda xon qarorgohi, salommxona joylashgan. Ikkinchi hovlida haram bo'lib, har birida nozik did bilan bezatilgan o'tish ayvonlari bo'lgan. Quyma ganchdan ko'p foydalanilgan. O'rda devorlari pishiq g'ishtdan ko'tarilgan bo'lib, ko'plab ravoqlar qoldirilgan. Obida ustalik bilan handasiy naqshlar va parchinlar bilan pardozlangan. Har bir xona o'yima ganchkori qilinib, shiftlarga nafis va rangdor gullar ishlangan. Devorlar noyob va takrorlanmas naqshlar bilan ziynatlangan. Ayvonlar sahniga qimmatbaho marmarlar mohirlik bilan yotqizilgan. Tashrif buyurgan inson dabdaba va shohonalik og'ushida o'zini bir lahza xon deb his etadi.

Vatanimiz hududida bularga o'xshash yuzlab obidalar mavjud. Agarda yoshlarni bu qadamjolariga olib borilsa, ular naqadar buyuk yurt farzandlari va dono insonlarning avlodlari ekanligini yana bir bor anglab yetadi. Bunday obidalar nafaqat o'sha davr uchun, balki hozirgi davr uchun xizmat ko'rsatib kelmoqda. Ularning bugungi kundagi o'rni yurtimizga sayyohlarni jalb etayotgani va butun dunyoga O'zbekiston nomini tanitayotgani bilan baholanadi.

XULOSA

Qachonki inson o'zligini, azaliy qadriyat va an'analarini unutar yoki ularga ularga biroz bo'lsa ham befarqlik bilan qarar ekan ma'naviy tahdidlarga duch keladi va unga yengiladi. Shu sababdan ham yurtimizda bu kabi tarixiy obidalar doimo yosh avlodga biz kim ekanligimiz, kimning avlodlariligimiz va albatta kelajakda nimalarga erisha olishimiz mumkinligini eslatib turuvchi qo'ng'iroq singari bong urib turaveradi.

Obidalar qurilishida tarbiyaviy jihatlar ham alohida e'tiborga olingan bo'lib, bunga yorqin misol tariqasida obidalardagi har bir hujraning eshiklari inson bo'yidan past qilib yasalganligi, bu esa xonaga kirayotganda u yerda o'tirgan shaxsga nisbatan egilib xurmat bajo qilishga inson beixtiyor majbur bo'lganini anglatganligidir. Bu ham sharq ma'naviy tarbiyasining o'ziga xos tomonlaridan biridir. Obidalarni o'z ko'zi bilan ko'rgan inson esa ko'plab bunday ajoyib va tarbiyaviy holatlarga duch keladi. Shu bois mana shunday ishlarni izchil amalga oshirish uchun yoshlarni tarixiy obidalar bilan yaqin tanishtirishimiz va ularni asrab-avaylashga o'rgatishimiz lozim. Ular bunday obidalar tarixini ming marta o'qib o'rgangandan ko'ra, bir marta borib ko'rganlari mqasadga muvofiqdir. Yoshlarni o'z yo'llaridan odimlab borishida bu kabi inson ruhiyatiga ma'naviy ozuqa beruvchi obidalarning o'rni beqiyosdir va buni hech narsa bilan baholab bo'lmaydi. Biz ularni asrashimiz, dovrug'ini yetti iqlimga yoyishda ko'maklashishimiz va kelajak avlodlarga asl holda yetkazishimiz zarur. Zero, bu yurtning har bir farzandi ushbu obidalar orqali o'tmish ulug'vorligidan ozuqa olishga haqlidir.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar ro'yxati:

1. Islom Karimov. "Yuksak ma'naviyat - yengilmas kuch". T.: "Ma'naviyat", 2008;
2. Axmedov B. "Sohibqiron Temur. Toshkent. 1996;
3. Boynanzarov Fayzulla. "Antik dunyo". "Mehnat" 1989;
4. Bahodir Eshov. "O'rta Osiyoning qadimgi shaharlari tarixi"- T.: "Ma'rifat", 2009.

Foydalanilgan saytlar:

5. www.meros.uz,
6. www.centrasia.com